

Data Architecture Checklist

To ensure best data architecture practices for research projects and institutions, we've compiled this checklist. This checklist comes in 2 sections, covering a total of 17 data architecture capabilities. The first section considers:

- existing data architecture
- data sources
- data format
- data types (structured, semi-structured or unstructured)
- data transformation techniques (ETL technologies)
- data pipelines and workflows
- data ingestion
- data storage
- data location (on-premises, cloud or hybrid)
- existing databases (relational and non-relational)
- data quality techniques
- data validation
- data decisions (data science, AI and ML)
- analytic support (visualisation).

The second section considers 3 further capabilities, which extend to architectures for systems, enterprise, infrastructure and others as well as data:

- data governance
- sensitive data
- FAIR principles.

DATA ARCHITECTURE CHECKLIST

Existing data architecture

- Do you have an existing data architecture?
- If yes, is the existing data architecture outdated, redundant, intractable and/or poorly aligned with your business requirements?
- If not, what are the current needs?

Data sources

- What are your data sources?
- How do you collect your data?
- Do you use sensor devices, interactive platforms, social media feeds and/or websites to gather the data?
- Are you using [APIs \(application programming interfaces\)](#) to retrieve data?

Data format

- Do you know the format of the data being collected (e.g. CSV, [JSON](#), [AVRO](#), [Parquet](#) and [Optimized Row Columnar \[ORC\]](#))?
- Are you using a specific metadata schema to describe your data (e.g. [Dublin Core](#), [Geospatial metadata \[ISO 19115\]](#) and [RIF-CS \[Registry Interchange Format for Collections and Services\]](#))?

Data types (structured, semi-structured, unstructured)

- Are you using structured data?
- Do you have semi-structured or unstructured data?

Data transformation techniques (ETL technologies)

- How is your data transformed (pre-processed) to make it analysis-ready? For example, are the datasets processed and organised into a form that allows immediate analysis?
- Are you using [extract, transform and load \(ETL\) processes](#) to clean and organise data?

Data pipelines and workflows

- Are there existing data pipelines or workflows?
- Do the data pipelines automate the manual steps involved in data transformation, such as data collection, cleansing, pre-processing and routing raw data to target systems?

Data ingestion

- Do you use [batch streaming](#)?
- Do you use [real-time streaming](#)?
- Have you considered [Lambda architecture](#)?

Data storage (on-premises, cloud or hybrid)

- What type of repository or data warehouse do you use to store your data?

Existing databases (relational and non-relational)

- How is your data organised? What type of database is used to store the data?

Data quality techniques

- Is there a data quality layer in the existing architecture to maintain the quality, integrity and accuracy of data?
- Have you removed information that is unneeded or duplicated?
- Are you performing regular [data profiling](#)?

Data validation

- Are you validating your data to check for any inconsistencies before consumption?

Data decisions (data science, AI and ML)

- Does the data architecture need modern technologies like data science, machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) for [data-driven decisions](#)?

Analytic support (visualisation)

- Is there a visualisation tool or process to visualise the data (e.g. [business intelligence \(BI\)](#) solutions together with real-time alerts, recommendations and predictions in BI reports and dashboards)?

CROSS-CAPABILITIES IN DATA ARCHITECTURE

Data governance

- Is governance in place for architecture? (Learn more about [data governance](#).)
- Is security in place to protect the data?

Sensitive data

- Are you [working with sensitive data](#)?

FAIR principles

- Has [the FAIR principles](#) been considered?
- Does the data architecture comply with FAIR data requirements? (Use our [tool for a FAIR assessment](#).)